

WRITING ERRORS OF JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS IN A RURAL SCHOOL AS REFLECTED IN THEIR PORTFOLIO

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 126

Issue 3

Pages: 276-282

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2463

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13902679

Manuscript Accepted: 09-07-2024

Writing Errors of Junior High School Students in a Rural School as Reflected in their Portfolio

Ofelia P. Baguilat*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

Writing is a multifaceted skill, challenging both to impart and acquire, intertwined with other essential abilities like reading and listening. Yet, mastering writing fluency holds immense value for students, jobseekers, graduates, and professionals alike. This study delved into the writing aptitude of 152 Junior High School students, scrutinizing their portfolio submissions. Employing a descriptive research approach, data analysis centered on evaluating students' writing capabilities. The rubrics used in evaluating students' output covers grammar, mechanics, and structure as the main aspects to be checked. The results uncovered a prevalent occurrence of grammatical errors, notably in verb forms and tenses, contrasted with fewer mechanical mistakes. Notably, age and grade level significantly influenced writing proficiency, while gender primarily impacted mechanics mastery. Moreover, the nature of writing errors varied across age, gender, and grade levels. These findings accentuate the necessity for customized instructional strategies to target specific grammatical weaknesses, alongside tailored support based on demographic characteristics to elevate overall writing competency among Junior High School students. By addressing these nuances, educators can effectively nurture proficient writers equipped for the challenges of academia and beyond.

Keywords: *grammar, junior high school, mechanics, structure, writing competencies*

Introduction

Proficiency in English encompasses various language skills essential for effective communication, including listening, speaking, reading, and writing. Each skill plays a vital role in linguistic development, with writing being a particularly intricate aspect that reflects one's mastery of language expression and coherence. Writing is a critical 21st century skill. Similarly, according to a recent study, the cover letter and resumes of job applicants lack evidence of social intelligence and the language used is not able to persuade the recruiter to shortlist the applicant for a job interview (Khairuddin and Mohamed, 2022). Though it is expected that elementary graduates show considerable proficiency in writing, Samina et. al (2021) found indications that the majority of the students at elementary level are unable to write grammatically precise English paragraphs. The findings of the study disclosed that the main problems of students' English writing are due to poor command over English tenses, grammar, syntax and insufficient vocabulary.

Disparities in writing skills both reflect and contribute to inequities in our society. Writing matters, and thus it is important to understand why so many students experience writing as deeply challenging and how they can be encouraged to develop their writing skills.

Educators acknowledge the pivotal role of writing in academic and professional success. However, studies from five years ago reveal that it is often undervalued in language courses, frequently confined to grammar exercises or simplistic tasks (Smith, 2019). Nevertheless, research highlights that the capacity to write coherently and effectively extends well beyond academic settings. It significantly influences one's ability to articulate thoughts, engage with complex ideas, and thrive in diverse spheres of life (Johnson, 2020).

Despite its challenges, writing offers unique opportunities for language learners. Recent studies continue to highlight the benefits of writing for language learners, emphasizing how writing offers opportunities for reflection, revision, and self-correction. These processes contribute to linguistic growth by allowing learners to internalize language structures in a more thoughtful and deliberate manner. Unlike oral communication, writing gives learners the space to revise and refine their thoughts before presenting them, which reduces the anxiety often associated with real-time spoken interactions.

However, writing difficulties are not exclusive to second language learners. Despite having learned English at the secondary or university level, students tend to make many grammatical errors in their writing (Fitrawati and Safitri, 2021). Such challenges underscore the need for comprehensive writing instruction and ongoing support across all educational levels.

In the Philippines, despite the efforts of the educational sector to improve students' writing skills, many students still experience difficulties in academic writing (Roxas, 2020). Students' struggles with writing are evident in their compositions, reflecting confusion, linguistic limitations, and inadequate language training.

Addressing these challenges requires a multifaceted approach involving educators, curriculum planners, and school administrators. By identifying students' writing weaknesses and implementing targeted interventions, English teachers can enhance writing instruction and support student progress. Moreover, integrating writing more prominently within the curriculum and fostering collaboration across disciplines can further bolster students' writing skills and overall language proficiency.

In light of these considerations, this study aims to investigate the writing errors committed by junior high school students, shedding light on their challenges, needs, and areas for improvement. It also tries to determine the role played by age, sex and grade level affect

the areas where students find difficulty with when it comes to writing. Furthermore, it tries compare which aspect (grammar, structure and mechanics) do students commit the most errors. By elucidating these factors, educators and policymakers can develop informed strategies to cultivate writing proficiency and empower students for success in academic, professional, and personal endeavors.

Methodology

Research Design

The study used the descriptive survey method. Siedlecki (2020) defines descriptive research design as aiming to accurately describe events as they occur in their natural setting. This method helps in drawing conclusions based on the collected data and provides insights into the current conditions or trends related to the research topic. Specifically, error analysis was used to identify, classify, and analyze the types of errors the students make in their writing to understand common patterns of mistakes and their possible causes.

Respondents

The respondents of the study composed of 152 Junior High School students. Since the school is considerably small, only those who are attending their classes regularly and are able to complete their activities in their portfolio are included in the study. Each grade level has a lone section with heterogeneous learners.

Instrument

A survey questionnaire was used to obtain the year level, age, and gender of the respondents. From the submitted portfolios, three writing outputs per quarter were evaluated using a rubric developed by a rural school teacher in the same field. The rubrics is divided into three sub-skills, grammar, structure, and mechanics. Grammar, which has the highest score ranging from 22-25, measures effectiveness of the text, complexity of the sentences, agreement of tense, number, word order/function, articles, pronouns and prepositions. Structure scores vary from 18-20 as the highest. It evaluates fluent expression, clarity of ideas, conciseness, organization, logical sequencing, cohesiveness, sophistication of range, effective word/idiom choice and usage, and word form mastery. Mechanics, with 5 as the highest score, looks into errors in spelling, punctuation, capitalization and paragraphing.

Data Analysis

Frequencies and percentages were used to determine the profile of the respondents as to age, gender and grade level. Mean scores were used to compare the results of the analysis of the writing errors of the respondents. The relationship between the respondents' profile to their writing errors as well as the differences in their writing errors across the three subskills were analysed using the One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA).

Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows the profile of the Junior High School students as to age, sex, and grade level.

Table 1. Profile of Junior High School Students

	<i>Profile</i>	<i>Frequency n=152</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Age	12	38	25.00
	13	31	20.39
	14	13	8.55
	15	33	21.71
	16	27	17.76
Sex	17	10	6.57
	Male	59	38.82
Grade Level	Female	93	61.18
	Grade 7	48	31.57
	Grade 8	37	24.34
	Grade 9	34	22.36
	Grade 10	33	21.71

Table1 illustrates the profile of the students as to age. It reflects that most of the respondents are 12 years old which comprises 25% of the total number of respondents. This is because public schools already accept six years old pupils to enter Grade I, unlike before that Grade I learners should be seven years old. This can eventually decrease over time with the implementation of the RA 10533(K-12 Basic Education Curriculum) and the Republic Act No. 10157 (Universal Public Kindergarten Program) which mandate that Kindergarten entrants should not be more than five years of age.

As to sex, most of the respondents are female with 61% while the males are only 33%. It is a common observation that females outnumber the males in the class.

It also shows that most of the respondents come from the Grade 7 which can be the reason why their age profile is quite young. It is

also a trend in school that Grade 7 students compose the highest number of enrollees but this population eventually decreases as they go to the higher grade levels. Some of the students drop out of school, transfer to other schools or get married before graduating high school. It unveils the truth that out of 100 learners, only 78 of them advance to the next grade level and this figure decreases as the levels increase. This can also be attributed to dropping out of students due to many factors like child labor and early marriage.

Table 2 presents the writing errors of Junior High School students in the three subskills.

Table 2. *Writing Errors of Junior High School Students*

	<i>Errors Committed</i>	<i>Average No. of Errors</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Grammar	Verb Forms and Tenses	35.07	1
	S-V Agreement	21.75	2
	Use of nouns	14.13	5
	Use of articles	13.01	6
	Use of Pronouns	14.90	3
	Use of Adjectives	14.66	4
	Total	113.43	1st
Structure	Coordination and Subordination	19.01	2
	Arrangement of Parts	11.65	4
	Ambiguity	11.78	3
	Overloadedness/wordiness	20.10	1
	Total	62.53	2nd
Mechanics	Capitalization	26.66	1
	Spelling	13.26	2
	Abbreviation	9.08	4
	Punctuation	12.96	3
	Total	61.96	3rd

Table 2 shows the writing errors of the Junior High School Students as reflected in their portfolio. It can be gleaned that they excel in using articles but commit most errors in using the correct verb forms and tenses in grammar. For structure, they perform well in arranging the parts of the paragraph but commit most mistakes in overloadedness/wordiness. They excel in abbreviations but make the most mistakes in capitalization in terms of mechanics.

In the grammar subskill, the students committed most errors in verb forms and tenses, followed by subject-verb agreement, and use of pronouns.

For instance, a student wrote, “They considered as my friends, our true friend.” From the context of the writing activity, the student meant that they (her friends) consider her as their true friend but the inability to use correct terms made the sentence erroneous.

These errors may be caused by the students’ lack of mastery in grammar in detail, forgetfulness of grammar rules though they have learnt it, and having limited vocabularies (Ayu, et.al, 2020). It agrees with Phommavongsa, et. al (2021) and Alghazo and Alshraideh (2020) who identified verb-tense as the topmost grammatical error committed by the students and Batubara, Rahila, & Rahmadani (2021) who pinpointed that nouns, verb tense, action words and linking verbs are areas where students commit the most errors. Moreover, Kampookaew (2020) also found that even Thai university students have prevalent errors in grammar, particularly on wrong use of singular and plural nouns, omission of the article ‘the’, and subject-verb disagreements.

For the structure, the students’ sentences were too wordy or overloaded. There were evident errors in coordination and subordination, and in stating their ideas clearly. Example of this is when a student wrote, “The person who inspired me is my mother because she is kind industrious and she strong in every problem that come to us.” For context, the learners were asked to write a descriptive paragraph about a person who inspired them. The errors in spelling, coordination, and verb use is very evident which hinders the clear delivery of what the student intended to convey. Yani (2022) attributes errors in writing to students’ indifference to their writing. It could also be due to lack of vocabulary, difficulty in conveying and organizing ideas, pupils’ perception that writing is a hard task, lack of motivation and interest in writing; and the difficulty in spelling, grammar and sentence construction (Saavedra, 2020).

Mechanical mistakes, on the other hand, are specified as errors in capitalization, spelling, and punctuation similar to Sami (2022) who found out that Kurdish students commit the most errors in punctuation and capitalization. Abolghasem & Fatemeh (2020) also stated that spelling and vocabulary errors are most common among the students that they studied. While vocabulary errors are caused by the students’ lack of familiarity with and incomplete learning of the target language (Persian), spelling errors are the outcome of their poor listening skill, inability to recognize vowels and semivowels, and weakness of visual memory. Moreover, Gildore, Uka, and Yting, (2023) also found mechanics as the most problematic aspect in written compositions of Senior High School students.

Some commonly misspelled words are “because” and “their” (in contrast with there) and words with double letters like “occur” and “occasion”. Most often, students fail to capitalize beginning letters of proper nouns within the sentences. Also, most of them do not cut

very long sentences into more concise statements for easier understanding.

Table 3 illustrates the writing errors of students when grouped according to age.

Table 3. *Writing Errors of Students when Grouped According to Age*

Errors	Age	Ave. No. of Errors	F-value	p-value	Remarks
Grammar	12	127.79	23.053	0.000	Significant
	13	125.29			
	14	124.92			
	15	106.15			
	16	89.19			
	17	96.60			
Structure	12	72.29	63.067	0.000	Significant
	13	65.16			
	14	63.62			
	15	59.24			
	16	52.70			
	17	53.30			
Mechanics	12	68.18	2.719	0.022	Significant
	13	65.45			
	14	65.77			
	15	55.94			
	16	58.74			
	17	51.10			

Table 3 illustrates the ANOVA Results of the writing errors of the students and their age. It reveals that there is significant difference in the writing competencies when grouped by age. The younger the students, the higher they commit error in terms of grammar, structure and mechanics. This is because the younger students have less exposure to writing activities where their mistakes are corrected and shown to them for rewriting. As Grenner (2020) asserts, young students may not be able to differentiate between self-efficacy, general writing skills, task performance, and self-regulation.

Composing text is a complex and difficult undertaking that requires the deployment and coordination of multiple affective, cognitive, linguistic, and physical operations to accomplish goals associated with genre-specific conventions, audience needs, and an author's communicative purposes. Even prolific authors find writing challenging.

It implies that age and maturity are directly proportional to the quality of written outputs of the learners since mastery and acquaintance with a richer vocabulary as well as mastery of the rules of writing are acquired from experiences through the years.

Table 4 shows the writing errors of students when grouped according to sex

Table 4. *Writing Errors of the Respondents when Grouped according to Sex*

	Sex	Mean	t-value	p-value	Remarks
grammar	Female	113.63	0.140	0.889	Not Significant
	Male	113.10			
structure	Female	62.11	0.763	0.447	Not Significant
	Male	63.20			
mechanics	Female	59.52	2.01	0.047	Significant
	Male	65.81			

Table 4 illustrates the ANOVA Results between the writing competencies of the students and their sex. It shows that there is no significant difference in the committed by male and female students as to grammar and structure. On the other hand, female students have significantly lower number of errors than their male

counterpart in terms of mechanics. Male students have historically under-performed in writing tasks compared to their female counterparts. This may be due to what Loureiro, et.al. (2020) found out that female students showed more significant levels of anxiety with regard to oral and written communication than male students. Anatomically, Yang, et. al (2020) explained that "compared to females, males showed increased activation in the left posterior middle frontal gyrus (Exner's area), a region thought to support the conversion between orthographic and graphomotor codes. Functional connectivity between Exner's area and the right cerebellum was greater in males than in females. Furthermore, sex differences in brain activity related to handwriting were independent of language material." This was also proven by Zulhaika (2020) who discovered that clear evidence shows that females generally had better English language proficiency, were more fluent writers and produced better text than males in Arabic and English.

Writing Errors of Students when Grouped according Grade Level

Table 3.5. ANOVA Results Between Writing Errors of the Students and their Grade Level

Error	Grade Level	Mean	F-value	p-value	Remarks
grammar	7	128.27	50.444	0.000	Significant
	8	124.73			
	9	105.06			
	10	87.79			
structure	7	72.40	246.52	0.000	Significant
	8	63.38			
	9	58.50			
	10	51.39			
mechanics	7	72.48	13.54	0.000	Significant
	8	64.92			
	9	55.74			
	10	49.76			

There is significant difference in the writing competencies when grouped by grade level. The lower the grade level, the higher they commit error in terms of grammar, structure and mechanics. Thus, students in the higher grade level have better competency than the students in the lower grades.

This is because as students progress through the grade levels, they acquire skills necessary for them to improve their competencies in the different macroskills. Students in the higher grade levels also have the metacognitive ability so they check their own mistakes when they notice that their statement is incorrect. It could be deduced that they already have a fuller understanding of what they learned. There is retention of knowledge about grammar, mechanics and structure. This is supported by Skar, et.al (2022) who found that handwriting fluency increased from one grade to the next, girls had faster handwriting than boys, and gender differences increased across grades. Also, an identical pattern of results were observed for writing quality.

This finding can also be traced to the structure of the Curriculum Guides and Learners' Materials provided by the Department of Education. The use of modules and learning packages in Grade 7 K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum becomes the tailored instructional technique that may suit best to the students' ability. However, the Learning Packages in English 7 are not in congruence with the Curriculum Guide which makes instruction difficult. The same can be observed with the Grade 8 English Learners' Materials and there are no sufficient copies for the learners to use. On the other hand, the Grades 9 and 10 modules are more comprehensive and copies are already complete for the effective delivery of the learning competencies. Grammar lessons, particularly subject-verb agreement should be emphasized in Grade 7 but is not fully stressed due to insufficient materials for the students to learn. Aside from this, there are too many learning competencies in English that the student should master in every quarter, thus grammar lessons, which are usually embedded in the literature topics, are somewhat taken for granted.

Conclusions

The students are averagely 12 years old, female, and in Grade 7.

The students commit more errors in grammar, particularly on using verb forms and tenses, subject-verb agreement, and use of pronouns in their writeups. In terms of structure, their errors are more on overloadedness/wordiness, coordination and subordinations, and ambiguity. Also, the students committed more errors in capitalization, spelling, and punctuation as to mechanics.

Age and Grade Level affect the writing errors committed by the students across all subskills, grammar, structure, and mechanics. The younger and lower the grade level of the students, the more errors are committed in writing, and as the students grow older, their writing errors significantly decrease.

Sex does not affect grammar and structure but has significant effects on errors in mechanics. Females excel more in using the rules of capitalization, spelling and punctuation than their male counterpart.

Students in the Junior High School are more competent in applying the rules of structure and mechanics than in using the rules of grammar in their writing outputs, specifically on verb forms and tenses.

Writing activities for high school students can be designed to be age-specific to ensure that the competencies desired of them will be achieved.

More emphasis can be given to grammatical rules, particularly on verb forms and tenses, to address issues regarding these competencies.

Strategic Intervention Materials may be developed to address least learned competencies along grammar especially in the lower grades

where younger students need supplemental materials to improve their writings skills.

Activities may also be tailored to gender-sensitive materials to cater to the different needs of male and female learners.

More grammar lessons and activities may be given to the students to improve their skills in this competency.

Further studies is recommended to explore more age and sex-appropriate strategies and or interventions that will help improve grammatical competence of students.

References

Abolghasem, G. & Fatemeh, J. (2020). Analysis of Common Writing Errors in Non-Persian Speakers (A Case Study of Written Texts at General Level in Persian Language Center of Imam Khomeini International University of Qazvin). *ZABANPAZHUIH (Iranian Journal of Language Research)*, Volume:12, Issue:34 (203-204) Retrieved from <https://www.sid.ir/paper/406702/en>

Alghazo, K. & Alshraideh, M. (2020). Grammatical Errors Found in English Writing: A Study from Al-Hussein Bin Talal University. *International Education Studies*; Vol.13, No. 9, doi:10.5539/ies.v13n9p1

Ayu, I. et.al (2020). Grammatical Errors in Students' Writing: Descriptive Study on Grade 7 Students. *Journal of English Language and Culture*, 11 (1). pp. 23-38. ISSN 2597-8896

Batubara, M. H., Rahila, C. D. I., & Rahmadani, P. (2021). An Analysis on the Students' Error in Writing Report Text at Eight Grade Students of SMP N 6 Timang Gajah. *Jurnal As-Salam*, 5(1), 10–19. <https://doi.org/10.37249/assalam.v5i1.237>

Fitrawati and Safitri, D. (2021). Students' Grammatical Errors in Essay Writing: A Pedagogical Grammar Reflection. *International Journal of Language Education* Volume 5, Number 2, 2021, pp. 74-88 ISSN: 2548-8457 (Print) 2548-8465 (Online) Doi: <https://doi.org/10.26858/ijole.v5i2.15241>

Gildore, P. J., Uka, A. H., & Yting, J. (2023). Error Analysis of Academic Essays of Senior High School Students. *Journal Corner of Education, Linguistics, and Literature*, 3(2), 141–156. <https://doi.org/10.54012/jcell.v3i2.224>

Grenner, E., Johansson, V., van de Weijer, J., & Sahlén, B. (2020). Effects of intervention on self-efficacy and text quality in elementary school students' narrative writing. *Logopedics Phoniatrics Vocology*, 46(1), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14015439.2019.1709539>

Johnson, R. (2020). The broader impacts of coherent writing: Beyond academic success. *Educational Review Quarterly*, 58(2), 87-102.

Khairuddin, A., & Mohamed, S. (2022). Social intelligence and persuasive language in job applications: An analysis of cover letters and resumes. *Journal of Employment and Career Development*, 37(4), 45-59.

Kampookaew, P. (2020). An Analysis of Grammatical Errors Made by Thai EFL University Students in an EAP writing Class: Issues and Recommendations. *rEFLections* Vol 27, No 2, July - December 2020, Retrieved from <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1283248>

Loureiro, M., Loureiro N., and Silva, R. (2020). Differences of Gender in Oral and Written Communication Apprehension of University Students. *Education Sciences*, Vol.10, no. 12: 379. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci10120379>

Phommavongsa, K., Xaysetha, S. & Phomchaleun, S. (2021). The Common Grammatical Errors in Writing Narrative Essay of Students at the Youth Resource Center, Savannakhet. *Jurnal Penelitian Humaniora*, Vol.22, No.1 (1-13) DOI: 10.23917/humaniora.v22i1.11501

Roxas, M.D. (2020). Exploring Senior High School Students' Academic Writing Difficulties: Towards an Academic Writing Model. *IOER International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, Volume 2, Issue 1, March 2020, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3545988>

Saavedra, A. (2020). Factors that Contribute to the Poor Writing Skills in Filipino and English of the Elementary Pupils. *International Journal on Innovation, Creativity and Change*. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3697915>

Sami, H. (2022) English Writing Errors of Kurdish EFL Undergraduates: An Error Analysis. *International Journal of Social Sciences & Educational Studies*, 9 (2). Retrieved from <https://eprints.tiu.edu.iq/1069/>

Samina, S. et.al (2021). Problems and Factors affecting students English writing skills at elementary level. *Ilkogretim Online*, 2021, Vol 20, Issue 5, p3079. 1305-3515. doi 10.17051/ilkonline.2021.05.332

Siedlecki, S. (2020). Understanding Descriptive Research Designs and Methods. *Clinical Nurse Specialist CNS*, Vol. 34, pages 8-12, DOI 10.1097/NUR.0000000000000493

Skar, G.B., Lei, P.W., Graham, S. et al. (2022). Handwriting fluency and the quality of primary grade students' writing. *Read Writ* 35, 509–538 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11145-021-10185-y>

Smith, J. (2019). The undervaluation of writing in language courses: A five-year review. *Journal of Language Education*, 45(3), 221-235.

Yani, K. (2022). Students' Error in Writing Descriptive Text in the Junior High School Viewed from its Indicators. *Jurnal Pendidikan Bahasa Inggris Undiksha*, Vol.9, No.3 Retrieved from <https://ejournal.undiksha.ac.id/index.php/JPBI/article/view/43351>

Yang, Y., et.al (2020). Men and women differ in the neural basis of handwriting. *Human Brain Mapping*, Vol.41, Issue 10 (2642-2655). <https://doi.org/10.1002/hbm.24968>

Zulaikha, A. (2020). Gender differences in writing: The mediating effect of language proficiency and writing fluency in text quality. *Cogent Education*, Vol. 7, DOI 10.1080/2331186X.2020.1770923

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Ofelia P. Baguilat

Nueva Vizcaya State University – Philippines